

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

PROSE OF ABDIZHAMIL NURPEISOV IN THE GERMAN LITERARY RECEPTION

Mashakova A.K.

PhD in Philology,

M.O.Auezov Institute of Literature and Art,

Almaty, Kazakhstan

Abstract

The article discusses the reception of the prose of the famous Kazakh writer Abdizhamil Nurpeisov by German professional readers, that is, literary critics and writers. The German authors of the reviews expressed their respect for the talent of the word master A. Nurpeisov. The process of literary translation of the trilogy "Blood and Sweat" and the novel "The Last Duty" into German is presented.

Keywords: reception, literary translation, Kazakh literature.

The creativity of the famous modern Kazakh prose writer Abdizhamil Nurpeisov plays a significant role in the foreign reception of Kazakh literature. The "Blood and Sweat" trilogy and the novel "The Last Duty" were translated into foreign languages and therefore became the object of attention and recognition from writers and critics in France, Germany, Belgium, Spain, Bulgaria, Slovakia, and China. This article will focus on the reception of A. Nurpeisov's creativity in Germany.

Literary translation is an important prerequisite for the reception of foreign literature. In Germany, the translation of A. Nurpeisov's works into German began with the "Blood and Sweat" trilogy. In Berlin, the Aufbau publishing house published the first book, "Twilight", in 1971, the second book, "The Ordeal", in 1972, and the third book, "The Crash", in 1975. All three books are translated by Wilhelm Plackmeier.

The appearance of the trilogy by A. Nurpeisov caused rave reviews from German literary critics and writers. A number of articles appeared in the popular newspapers and magazines "National Zeitung", "Der Morgen", "Neue Zeit", "Neue Deutsche Literatur", "Berliner Zeitung", "Kulturpolitik-Literatur", "Freie Welt".

The newspaper "Der Morgen" published an article "The Uprising of the Fishermen", which highlighted the importance of Kazakh literature: "Having deep roots in epic and lyrical poetry, which is supported by the people, it has changed and developed over the centuries. The richness of this literature is also felt in the novel "Twilight" by Abdizhamil Nurpeisov" [1]. The article emphasized the following distinctive features of the style of the Kazakh writer – straightforwardness and rigor in depicting the life of fishermen, a fairly realistic description of the harsh nature.

The article "Storm from yurts and fishing dug-outs" ("Neue Zeit") reveals the attractiveness of Nurpeisov's novel, which is due to "a deep connection with the people, a lively depiction of characters and a colorful description of exciting events" [2].

German literary critics Peter Kirchner and Gerlind König are in solidarity with these theses, who in the article "Changes in the life of the Kazakh people" drew attention to the credibility and expressiveness of depiction of characters in the novel, they noted "the symbolic

meaning of the images of nature, the steppe, the sea and their inclusion directly into the actions and events" [3].

In the article "Life Pictures", Ortwin Schubert noted that Nurpeisov, when depicting reliable historical events, pays great attention to describing the life, destinies and changing characters of living people: "Life pictures clearly and convincingly describe a turning point, changes in the minds and in the life of the Kazakh people" [4].

German authors expressed their respect for the talent of the master of words A. Nurpeisov. In the article "The Sun for the Disadvantaged", Peter Kirchner called A. Nurpeisov "an author who is characterized by an accurate, clearly expressed individual style and almost scientific objectivity of analysis" [5]. L. Peters characterizes A. Nurpeisov as a skillful storyteller. Introducing the second book of "The Ordeals" to the readers, he notes its value, which lies in the fact that the author "acquaints the readers with some people of his nation, with all their joys and anxieties, with their respectable qualities and their shortcomings" [6]. Another positive characteristic of the artistic excellence of A. Nurpeisov was expressed by Werner Neubert, who was personally acquainted with the Kazakh writer. In his opinion, A. Nurpeisov is a talented and gifted Kazakh writer: "in the novel "The Crash", the writer's maturity is clearly manifested in terms of highly individual-human and ideal-moral qualities" [7].

In 1979, an article dedicated to A. Nurpeisov was published in the German literary encyclopedia "Lexikon fremdsprachiger Schriftsteller". Its author, the German translator Eckhard Thiele, covered the main periods of the life and creative path of the Kazakh writer, and special attention was paid to the trilogy "Blood and Sweat" [8]. It is noteworthy that E. Thiele was familiar with Kazakh literature, as he translated into German the novels "Dashing Time" by Mukhtar Auezov and "Wormwood and Flowers" by Dukenbai Doszhanov.

In 1989, the Bertelsmann publishing house in Munich published the novel "The Last Duty" under the title "Der sterbende See" ("The Dying Sea"). The translation into German was made by Wilhelm Plackmeier, who is already familiar with the translation of the "Blood and Sweat" trilogy. The appearance of the novel

“The Dying Sea” in Germany was accompanied by responses in the German newspapers “Grosslarische Zeitung” (the article “A direct path to disaster. A novel about the drying up of the Aral Sea”), “Rundschau am Sonntag” (the article “The Dying Sea”). In addition, reviews by Gudrun Ziegler, Ulrich Braun, Clara Obermuller appeared in the German press. Environmental problems are familiar to German readers, and so the compassion for the inhabitants of the Aral region, who are experiencing an environmental catastrophe, unites the above articles.

According to G. Ziegler, A. Nurpeisov is “not the only one among modern Soviet writers who with increased persistence expresses the environmental problems in a novel form. I immediately remember such names as Valentin Rasputin and Chingiz Aitmatov. Still, we are dealing here with one of the most interesting Soviet novels of recent years. The novel “The Dying Sea” by Abdizhamil Nurpeisov has many advantages” [9]. Analyzing the excellence of the Kazakh writer, G. Ziegler draws attention to the author’s observation, who intertwines the human, animal and nature so proportionately into the mode of the general collapse that it makes one feel compassion at a distance of thousand kilometers. “And this is a beneficial compassion, as we have discovered a talent that draws its ability from a confidential dialogue with old traditions and bitter modernity. This discovery is due to a remarkable translation” [9].

Assessing the significance of the novel “The Dying Sea”, K. Obermuller characterizes it as follows: “Abdizhamil Nurpeisov’s story about the fisherman Zhadyger, his opponent, the careerist Azim, and the young Bakizat who is between them is a literary and political document, which, like a slowly flowing river, is either epically alive describing, or convincingly monologizing, recreates a stunning picture of a decaying, perishing culture” [10].

A. Nurpeisov took an active part in public life, and in international events, therefore many foreign reviews and responses are due to his personal contacts with figures of foreign literature. In this case, we should mention Leonard Kossuth, who was personally acquainted with A. Nurpeisov.

Leonard Kossuth repeatedly visited Kazakhstan and published his memories of meetings with A. Nurpeisov in an autobiographical book which is dedicated to the history of the Volk und Welt publishing house. The book was published in 2002 in Berlin. It consists of 37 chapters, one of which is devoted to Kazakhstan. In this chapter, the author tells about his meetings with famous Kazakhstani writers, poets and about the publication of their works in the GDR. So, L. Kossuth tells about one of his trips to Kazakhstan, when, at the invitation of A. Nurpeisov, he spent two weeks on Kazakh land, met writers and ordinary people. An interesting fact was that a Kazakh girl was named after the wife of L. Kossuth. “Sixteen years later, the Kazakh Charlotte was invited to visit us in Berlin with her parents” [11, p.138].

As for the friendly relations between L. Kossuth and A. Nurpeisov, they began from the time when his wife Charlotte was the editor of the publication of the

trilogy “Blood and Sweat” by A. Nurpeisov in the Berlin publishing house “Aufbau”. Charlotte Kossuth was fruitfully engaged in translations, for which she was awarded the prize “For outstanding achievements in the translation of fiction from foreign languages” (GDR).

In 2002, the German magazine “Ossietzky” published an article “When the Sea Disappears” by L. Kossuth about A. Nurpeisov’s novel “The Last Duty”. This is a review of the edition of the novel in Moscow in Russian, translated by Anatoly Kim and Herold Belger. L. Kossuth, thanks to a long-standing friendship with the author, had the opportunity to read this book. In the article, he openly called for the publication of this novel in Germany: “If our society was not so oriented towards the West, then the novel “The Last Duty”, authored by the Kazakh Abdizhamil Nurpeisov, would have been translated into German long ago and would have been evaluated as a great work of the world literature” [12, p.67].

This review of “The Last Duty” novel played an important role in the appearance of the German edition of this novel in Germany. In October 2006, the presentation of the novel ‘The Last Duty’ by A. Nurpeisov was successfully held in Berlin, Hamburg, Munich. It was translated by Annelore Nitschke. L. Kossuth involved her as a brilliant translator to this matter. And it was he who contributed to the publication of the work when, together with A. Nurpeisov, he visited the publishing house ‘Dagieli Verlag’ in Frankfurt am Main. Thus, the novel “The Last Duty” was published in German – the first work from which the series “Kazakhstan Library” begins in Germany.

The afterword to this book, which was published under the title ‘The Dying Sea’, was prepared by the editor of the Mario Pshera publishing house. The statement of the German author of the afterword regarding the role of the novel ‘The Dying Sea’ in the work of A. Nurpeisov is interesting: ‘Maybe this is his “last duty” to his people, his hope that the suffering and upheaval of the last century were not in vain’ [13, c.515]. According to M. Pshera, which is expressed at the end of the article, the experiences of A. Nurpeisov, expressed in his works, should help new generations find their way in life.

So, the reception of A. Nurpeisov’s prose in Germany can be called positive. German professional readers note the talent and excellence of the Kazakh writer in a realistic depiction of the events, and in covering environmental issues.

This work was carried out in the frame of the grant funding from the Science Committee of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan on the project AR08855803 “Kazakhstan and the world literary space: comparative studies” for 2020-2022.

References

1. Uprising of the fishermen // Der Morgen. 13.11.1971. No. 208 [in German].
2. Storm of yurts and fishing dugouts // Neue Zeit. 20.01.1972. No. 17 [in German].
3. Kirchner P., Koenig G. Changes in the life of the Kazakh people // Neue Deutsche Literatur. 11.12.1974. No. 12 [in German].

4. Schubert O. Life pictures // Der Morgen. 1975. No. 86. P. 9 [in German].
5. Kirchner P. The sun for the disadvantaged // Neues Deutschland Literatur. 09.02.1972. No. 2 [in German].
6. Peters L. A vivid picture of the life of the people from distant Kazakhstan // Berliner Zeitung. 05.05.1972. No. 124 [in German].
7. Neubert V. Abdizhamil Nurpeisov. Crash // Kulturpolitik-Literatur. 21.03.1975 [in German].
8. Thiele E. Nurpeisov Abdizhamil // Lexikon fremdsprachiger Schriftsteller. Von den Anfängen bis zu Gegenwart. Leipzig. 1979. P. 535 [in German].
9. Ziegler G. A bitter novel about the death of the Aral Sea // Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung. 25.11.1989 [in German].
10. Obermuller K. We hear one thing, but see another // Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung. 25.11.1989 [in German].
11. Kossuth L. Volk & Welt. Autobiographical evidence of a legendary publishing house. Berlin: Nora, 2002. 379 p. [in German].
12. Kossuth L. When the sea disappears // Ossietzky, Berlin-Hannover. 2002. No. 19. P. 67-69 [in German].
13. Pshera M. Afterword // Abdizhamil Nurpeisov. Dying sea. Berlin: Dayyeli Verlag, 2006. P. 513-515 [in German].